

BioDT and DestinE

*Collaboration to strengthen the
development of Digital Earth Twins*

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Goal of BioDT

Support Research Infrastructures for biodiversity by making a first **prototype digital twin** that **drives both science & uses cases** and **connects EU twins & initiatives**

Big Questions linked to Sustainable Development Goals

- 🔥 How will climate change affect biodiversity?
- 🔥 What can we do to mitigate loss of biodiversity?
- 🔥 How can we adapt to the new status-quo?
- 🔥 Will we be able to produce enough food?
- 🔥 Can we stay healthy?
- 🔥 Do we want to make Biodiversity and financial interests comparable?

Initial Twin

Current Twin Prototypes

Next Calls

Climate Change
Extreme Weather

- BioSphere
- Marine Life Biodiversity
- Ocean
- Hydrology
- CryoSphere
- Land Surface
- Atmosphere
- Localized City Twins
- EU Power grid
- And more...

- 🔥 Twin integration patterns

- 🔥 Embedded: directly integrated in the Destination Earth system

- 🔥 Tightly-Coupled: integrated in a workflow where new digital twins interface with the Destination Earth digital twins

**Current
Twins!**

- 🔥 Loosely-coupled: as post-processing applications without own Destination Earth-system

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When?

How?

	Biodiversity RIs, RI nodes, data providers and researchers RIs, universities, research organisations; the end-users that will contribute to developing the DT, enhancing its use cases, and testing its functionalities
	Policy makers EU, Member States, Local governments, intergovernmental organisations (UNESCO, FAO, etc.)
	Industrial actors incl. SMEs Sectors related to biodiversity, such as agri-food, tourism, healthcare.
	Civil society and citizen scientists

	<p>Biodiversity RIs, RI nodes, data providers and researchers</p> <p>Better understanding of nature: High quality models, increased data coverage, more species aspects, increased science collaboration, widening field of biodiversity</p>
	<p>Policy makers</p> <p>Achievable policy: clear biodiversity metrics, mitigation strategies, socio / economic aspects of biodiversity, scenario planning</p>
	<p>Industrial actors incl. SMEs</p> <p>Engineering compliance supporting policy: Impact minimalization, design for diversity, changing role in ecosystem, Biodiversity services,</p>
	<p>Civil society and citizen scientists</p> <p>Nature Enthusiasm: Engaging with nature, helping data coverage, taking samples, stimulate local biodiversity, activate mitigation strategies</p>

- 🔥 Virtual environment for science

- 🔥 Set up personal data, experiment & validation
- 🔥 Low-code/less-code environment
- 🔥 Default scale-up to HPC/Cloud facilities
- 🔥 Fast results & experimentation
- 🔥 Easy transition of results

- 🔥 Sustainability supportive operations for industry

- 🔥 Tools that create yield AND support nature
- 🔥 Compliance by default for new permits
- 🔥 Tools offering mitigation services
- 🔥 Tools offering adaptation services

First aspects in development

- 🔥 Future planner for policy makers

- 🔥 Interactive environment
- 🔥 Evaluate future scenario's
- 🔥 Establish weights for social / economic / biodiversity
- 🔥 Based on proven models
- 🔥 Driving SDGs

- 🔥 Engagement for citizens

- 🔥 Create understanding of new policy
- 🔥 Activation & engagement apps

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**Still requires
much work**

- Sustainability supportive operations for industry

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To achieve these possible futures

- 🔥 Collaborate & create common:
 - 🔥 Language / way of speaking / way of working
 - 🔥 Set of goals/types and uses
 - 🔥 Interoperability & interfaces
 - 🔥 Leap in scientific scale & understanding
 - 🔥 Data, environments, code, validation tools
 - 🔥 Make twins far simpler to make and use
 - 🔥 Availability of data
 - 🔥 ...

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